

ABSTRACT

Title of Document: EFFECT OF ATMOSPHERIC AIR
PLASMA TREATMENT ON THE
SURFACE MORPHOLOGY,
WETTABILITY, WATER IMBIBITION,
AND GERMINATION OF CORN
KERNELS (ZEA MAYS)

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The study utilized atmospheric air plasma treatment for potential improvement in the germination of corn (*Zea mays*) due to enhanced water absorption. The seeds were divided into groups treated at varying durations: 1 second, 2 seconds, and 3 seconds. Wettability and water imbibition increased owing to the seed surface having the potential formation of oxygen and nitrogen-containing functional groups as confirmed present in the plasma by optical emission spectra analysis and to the surface etching revealed in the SEM images. However, only the 1s-treated group exhibited improvement in all germination attributes since longer plasma exposure causes more surface etching, thereby inflicting greater damage to the germ area.

EFFECT OF ATMOSPHERIC AIR PLASMA TREATMENT ON THE
SURFACE MORPHOLOGY, WETTABILITY, WATER IMBIBITION, AND
GERMINATION OF CORN KERNELS (ZEA MAYS)

By

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Dedication

This is for the people without whom this thesis would not have been completed, nor even conceived, and to whom I am greatly indebted.

To my family, with whom I have shared ups and downs, this thesis stands as a testament to your unconditional love and encouragement. Thank you for cheering me up with calls and messages every week – despite my own limited devotion to correspondence.

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Table of Contents

Dedication	i
Acknowledgements	ii
Table of Contents	iii
List of Tables	iv
List of Figures	v
Chapter 1: Introduction	1
1.1. Background of the study	1
1.2. Significance of the study	1
1.3. Statement of the problem	2
1.4. Scope and delimitations	2
Chapter 2: Review of Related Literature	3
2.1. Introduction to atmospheric air plasma	3
2.2. Introduction to germination	4
2.3. Plasma technology in agriculture	4
Chapter 3: Methodology	6
3.1. Seed material	6
3.2. Plasma system and treatment	6
3.3. OES of plasma	8
3.4. Scanning electron microscope imaging	8
3.5. Wettability test	8
3.6. Water imbibition test	8
3.7. Germination test	9
3.8. Statistical analysis	11
Chapter 4: Results and Discussion	12
4.1. OES of plasma	12
4.2. Effect on surface morphology	13
4.3. Effect on wettability	17
4.4. Effect on water imbibition	19
4.5. Effect on germination	19
4.6. Statistical Analysis	22
4.7. Correlation of surface morphology to wettability and water imbibition	23
4.8. Correlation of surface morphology and germination	23
Chapter 5: Conclusions and Recommendations	25
5.1. Conclusions	25
5.2. Recommendations	26
Appendices	27
References	36

List of Tables

Table C.1. ANOVA results for the germination attributes of white corn kernels based on germination count upon protrusion of the radicle: (a) germination percentage, (b) median germination time (t50) according to Coolbear et al., (c) median germination time (t50) according to Farooq et al., (d) mean germination time, and (e) coefficient of velocity of germination.	32
Table C.2. ANOVA results for the germination attributes of white corn kernels based on germination count once the radicle has reached half the length of the seed: (a) germination percentage, (b) median germination time (t50) according to Coolbear et al., (c) median germination time (t50) according to Farooq et al., (d) mean germination time, and (e) coefficient of velocity of germination.	34

List of Figures

Figure 2.1. The structure of a corn kernel. ^[18]	4
Figure 3.1. A schematic diagram of the atmospheric air plasma jet system.....	7
Figure 4.1. OES characterization of the atmospheric air plasma.....	12
Figure 4.2. SEM images of the endosperm area of the hull of yellow corn kernels which are (a) untreated (control); (b) exposed to plasma for 1s; (c) exposed to plasma for 2s; (d) exposed to plasma for 3s at a scale bar of 1mm.	14
Figure 4.3. SEM images of the tip cap of yellow corn kernels which are (a) untreated (control); (b) exposed to plasma for 1s; (c) exposed to plasma for 2s; (d) exposed to plasma for 3s at a scale bar of 200 μ m.	15
Figure 4.4. SEM images of the germ area of the hull of yellow corn kernels which are (a) untreated (control); (b) exposed to plasma for 1s; (c) exposed to plasma for 2s; (d) exposed to plasma for 3s at a scale bar of 200 μ m.	16
Figure 4.5. SEM images of the germ area of the hull of white corn kernels which are (a) untreated (control); (b) exposed to plasma for 1s; (c) exposed to plasma for 2s; (d) exposed to plasma for 3s at a scale bar of 100 μ m.	17
Figure 4.6. A time series graph showing the decrease in contact angles with longer treatment of yellow corn kernels at the germ area.	18
Figure 4.7. A time series graph showing the decrease in contact angles with longer treatment of yellow corn kernels at the endosperm area.....	18
Figure 4.8. A time series graph showing the increase in water imbibition of white corn kernels with longer treatment.	19
Figure 4.9. A comparison of germination percentage of yellow corn kernels treated at varying durations at the endosperm area.....	20
Figure 4.10. A comparison of germination percentage of white corn kernels treated at varying durations at the germ area.	20
Figure 4.11. Coefficient of velocity of germination of yellow corn kernels treated at the endosperm area and of white corn kernels treated at the germ area averaged for all trials at varying durations.	21
Figure 4.12. Median germination time and mean germination time of yellow corn kernels treated at varying durations at the endosperm area.	21
Figure 4.13. Median germination time and mean germination time averaged for all trials of white corn kernels treated at varying durations at the germ area.	22
Figure 4.14. Modified Timson's index of yellow corn kernels treated at the endosperm area and of white corn kernels treated at the germ area averaged for all trials at varying durations.....	22

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1. *Background of the study*

Corn is the second most important crop in the Philippines.^[1] White corn is the staple food of 20% of the Filipino population, next to rice,^[2] and yellow corn is a major component of many industrial products.^[3] Approximately 1.8 million farmers, or one-third, depend on corn as the major source of livelihood^[4] and annual production amounts to a total of around 8 million metric tons.^[5] As such, ways to improve its germination and yield have been widely explored, one of which is plasma technology.

1.2. *Significance of the study*

The relatively inexpensive pre-sowing treatment of seeds with low temperature atmospheric plasma has been proven safe and effective in boosting plant growth.^[6-8] The process does not involve chemicals and possible environmental pollutants. Carrying it out at atmospheric pressure also eliminates the need for complicated vacuum systems and leaves the biological samples unharmed since the low temperature reduces the risk of thermal damage^[9].

The plasma treatment mainly affects the hull, changing its wetting properties^[10] to accelerate germination. As a mixture of gases, air as a feeding gas promotes the formation of oxygen and nitrogen-containing functional groups on the treated surface,^[7,9,11] with its low cost and availability providing even more incentive for its application. Exposure to air plasma also breaks dormancy^[12] and controls infection due to fungal and bacterial plant pathogens,^[9,13-15] leading to greater yield.

1.3. Statement of the problem

This study investigated the effect of varying the duration of atmospheric air plasma treatment on the germination of corn kernels. For each treatment time variation, germination attributes were computed based on the daily count of germinated seeds over a period of 120 hours. The results were correlated with the presence of certain species in the optical emission spectra (OES) of plasma and the observed changes in the properties of seeds, namely – surface morphology, wettability, and water imbibition.

1.4. Scope and delimitations

This study focused on characterizing the effects of plasma treatment on the surface morphology, wettability, water imbibition, and germination of corn kernels. The effect of plasma treatment on the growth and yield of the corn plant was not covered in this study. A set parameter for the plasma was used and the independent variable was the treatment duration. Although the ions present in the plasma were identified, the experiments did not include an analysis of the polar functional groups which may have formed in the seed surface after plasma treatment.

Chapter 2

Review of Related Literature

2.1. *Introduction to atmospheric air plasma*

Over 99% of the matter in the universe is believed to be plasma state; that is, an “ionized” gas comprised of electrons and ions exhibiting a neutral charge.^[16] In general, there are two types of plasmas: equilibrium or “thermal” plasmas and non-equilibrium or “cold” plasmas. Equilibrium plasmas consist of ionized gas with equal or almost equal energies of electrons, ions, and neutrals. This requires the gas to be heated to very high temperatures. On the other hand, non-equilibrium plasmas may have high energy electrons independent of the ions and neutrals. Hence, the temperature may be low or even equal to room temperature, widening the applications to treating materials that are sensitive to temperature, such as biological tissues.^[11]

However, non-equilibrium plasmas usually exist only in low pressures, and they can be created in the laboratory by pumping air out of a vacuum chamber. Nevertheless, it is still possible to generate plasma at atmospheric pressure. Atmospheric plasma is produced without complicated vacuum systems, saving space, time, and cost.^[17] This makes them more viable for wide scale purposes such as in the industry.

Depending on the application, the feeding gas may range from helium, nitrogen, argon, a combination of gases, or even air. Plasma produces charged particles, radicals, ions, high-energy electrons, and UV emission that may interact with the surface.^[11] Low temperature plasma treatment often involves surface modification, which is induced by the bombardment of reactive species.

2.2. Introduction to germination

The germination process starts with imbibition, wherein the seeds undergo rapid initial water uptake. This is followed by a plateau phase characterized by high metabolic activity, but little change in water content, and lastly, by radicle protrusion from the germ area in Figure 2.1^[18] and growth of the seedling, which are accompanied by increased water content.^[19]

Figure 2.1. The structure of a corn kernel.^[18]

The germination percentage and mean germination rate have been used to analyze the effects of treatments to the seed.^[8,20] Other germination metrics considered in previous studies are median germination time, which refers the time to reach 50% of final or maximum germination; mean germination time, which refers to the average length of time required for maximum germination of a seed lot; coefficient of velocity of germination, which has also been called Kotowski's coefficient of velocity; and modified Timson's index which emphasizes on both the percentage of germination and its speed.^[21]

2.3. Plasma technology in agriculture

Several treatments have been studied for their effects on the germination of various seeds. Among these are physical scratching, heat treatment, and chemical treatment.

However, these processes have limitations, such as high risks of destroying the seeds and polluting the environment. Recently, low temperature plasma treatment has been investigated as an effective, yet safe, cheap, and environment-friendly alternative for the improvement of germination and growth of different plant species. The plasma has an advantage of more uniform treatment, less risk of seed destruction, and less environmental waste since the plasma process does not require chemicals. Additionally, seed storage is also possible after plasma treatment. [6]

Junior^[22] utilized a plasma jet produced by dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) in a helium gas flow of 0.03 L/s. After exposing the seeds to plasma for 60 seconds at a distance of 13 mm, the findings showed accelerated germination rate and reduced apparent contact angle.

Bormashenko^[10] also noticed added hydrophilicity. This caused a significant drop in the apparent contact angle and a boost in the water imbibition, thereby increasing the germination rate. These changes in water permeability were correlated with the decrease in surface roughness of lentils, beans, and wheat seeds after cold radio frequency air plasma treatment at 10MHz of 20W. Furthermore, the plasma-treated seeds showed a higher concentration of oxygen- and nitrogen-containing groups at the surface.

Filatova et al.^[9,15] found that the reactive species of oxygen atoms and molecules present in air plasma even provided fungicidal and bactericidal effects. It was observed that low-pressure air plasma of the 5.28 MHz RFCD treatment stimulates germination, shoot growth, and root development of maize, spring wheat, and lupinus.

Similarly, Jiang et al.^[23] concluded that cold helium plasma treatment stimulated the germination and promoted the growth of wheat, leading to increased yield.

Chapter 3

Methodology

3.1. *Seed material*

The seeds were sourced from Bukidnon, Philippines. Two varieties of corn kernels without any visible defects were utilized in the experiments – the yellow corn initially treated with Gaucho® 600 Insecticide and Apron XL® Fungicide and the white corn. The seeds were stored in labelled, air-tight plastic containers until used in the experiments.

3.2. *Plasma system and treatment*

The atmospheric plasma jet system shown in Figure 3.1 consisted of a borosilicate glass nozzle, two gas inlets, and one outlet with a diameter of 2.5 mm. It was equipped with two tungsten electrodes connected to a 450 W AC neon sign transformer that provided up to 15 kV potential difference at a frequency of 60 Hz. The input RMS voltage of 232 V and current of 1.99 A, which were measured using an Alexan AC2000 multimeter.^[24] Air was pumped through the inlets with a PT310 AC air compressor at a maximum flow rate of 25 cfm to discharge the plasma at the outlet.

Figure 3.1. A schematic diagram of the atmospheric air plasma jet system.

Different seeds were utilized for the scanning electron microscope imaging, wettability test, water imbibition test, and germination test. Each seed was placed in a rotating acrylic disk at 2 mm below the nozzle at a gas temperature of 160 °C as measured by a thermocouple. The plasma exposure time for seeds were varied as follows: 1s, 2s, and 3s. Movement of corn seeds under the nozzle was carried out mechanically to ensure their uniform treatment. An Arduino microcontroller was used for a discontinuous run of the DC motor, such that the acrylic disk stops rotating for the specified duration at 0.5-second intervals. The seed samples without treatment served as the control.

3.3. OES of plasma

The OES of the plasma discharge was obtained with USB4000 Ocean Optics and SpectraSuite software under the treatment conditions. The species present were identified using the Spectrum Analyzer 1.7 software.^[25]

3.4. Scanning electron microscope imaging

Changes in the surface morphology of different parts of the hull – the endosperm area, the tip cap, and the germ area, as illustrated in Figure 2.1,^[18] were observed before and after plasma treatment of the yellow corn kernel. Only the germ area was observed before and after plasma treatment of the white corn kernel. The seeds were subjected to scanning electron microscope imaging using the Hitachi TM-1000 Tabletop SEM.

3.5. Wettability test

Nine trials each of yellow corn kernels treated at the endosperm area and at the germ area were taken for each treatment time variation. Each seed was mounted on an adjustable platform horizontally aligned to the USB microscope camera, which is connected to a computer. Immediately after dropping 1 μL of deionized water with a Hamilton Micro Syringe on the seed surface, a snapshot was taken every ten seconds for one minute. The left and right contact angles were measured using the DropSnake Java plug-in for the ImageJ software^[26] and averaged to find the contact angle for each seed.

3.6. Water imbibition test

For each treatment time variation, the white corn kernels were grouped into three replicates of 15 seeds. Immediately after plasma treatment at the germ area, the dry weight of each group was recorded. These were then wrapped in task wipers

(Kimwipes) initially dampened with 15 mL deionized water, then stored in separate plastic containers. Every hour for four hours, each group of seeds was removed from the container, surface dried with task wipers, and weighed. The percent change in weight for each group of seeds was normalized by the corresponding dry weight. The resulting percent weight difference was plotted onto a graph with respect to the time elapsed.

3.7. Germination test

For the yellow corn kernels, nine seeds consisted each group of treatment time variation. Meanwhile, for the white corn kernels, three replicates of 45 seeds consisted each group of treatment time variation. After exposing the germ area to the plasma discharge, each group of seeds was stored in a plastic container. The seeds were kept in separate compartments, but they shared a bed of task wipers (Kimwipes) initially dampened with deionized water, 6 mL for the yellow corn kernels and 30 mL for the white corn kernels. All were grown for five days in a room with the air conditioning unit maintained at 25 °C. The temperature range was 24.7 °C to 25.2 °C and the humidity range was 67 % to 81 % as recorded by for the whole germination period. The LED light was controlled by a timer switch and kept on for 12 hours each day (6:00 AM – 6:00 PM). To maintain the moisture of the germination environment, another 3 mL and 15 mL of deionized water were added on Day 2 for the yellow corn kernels and the white corn kernels respectively.

The number of germinated seeds was counted every day. Two standards of germination count were employed – one which considers seeds upon protrusion of the radicle,^[10,27] and another that considers seeds once the radicle has reached half the length of the seed.^[23] The germination attributes were computed using the R package *germinationmetrics* according to the following formulas:^[21]

$$GP = \frac{N_g}{N_t} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where, N_g is the number of germinated seeds and N_t is the total number of seeds. A higher germination percentage (GP) value implies a greater germination of a seed population. However, GP only reflects the final percentage of germination attained and provides no picture of the speed or uniformity of germination.

$$CVG = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k N_i}{\sum_{i=1}^k N_i T_i} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where, T_i is the time from the start of the experiment to the i th observation, T_i is the number of seeds germinated in the i th time (not the accumulated number, but the number correspondent to the i th observation), and k is the last time of germination. The coefficient of velocity of germination (CVG) gives an indication of the rapidity of germination. It increases when the number of germinated seeds increases and the time required for germination decreases. Theoretically, the highest CVG possible is 100, which is the case if all seeds germinated on the first day.

$$MGT = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k N_i T_i}{\sum_{i=1}^k N_i} \quad (3)$$

The mean germination time (MGT) reflects seed vigor. The lower the MGT, the faster the sample has germinated. However, some authors recommend median germination time (t_{50}) for treatment comparisons:^[28]

$$t_{50} \text{ by Coolbear et. al} = T_i + \frac{\left(\frac{N+1}{2} - N_i\right)(T_j - T_i)}{N_j - N_i} \quad (4)$$

$$t_{50} \text{ by Farooq et. al} = T_i + \frac{\left(\frac{N-N_i}{2}\right)(T_j - T_i)}{N_j - N_i} \quad (5)$$

where, N is the final number of germinated seeds and N_i and N_j are the total number

of seeds germinated in adjacent counts at time T_i and T_j respectively, when $N_i < \frac{N}{2} < N_j$.

$$T_{\text{mod}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^t g_i (t - j)}{\sum_{i=1}^t g_i} \quad (6)$$

where, g_i is the partial germination percentages in time interval and t is the total number of time intervals and $j = i - 1$. In the modified Timson's index (T_{mod}), maximum weight is given to the seeds germinated on the first day and less to those germinated later. The lowest weight would be for seeds germinated on the last day. A higher T_{mod} value denotes a higher percentage and rate of germination.

3.8. Statistical analysis

The data gathered were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the Real Statistics Resource Pack software (Release 5.4) for Microsoft Excel.^[29] Data with p-value < 0.05 was considered significant.

Chapter 4

Results and Discussion

4.1. *OES of plasma*

OES characterization of the atmospheric plasma depicted in Figure 4.1 detected N₂, O₂, NO, CO, and CN species. This confirms that the air used to generate plasma and the atoms and molecules surrounding the system were ionized in the process.

Figure 4.1. OES characterization of the atmospheric air plasma.

The presence of N, O, and NO species implies a high probability of chemical changes and oxidation occurring on the surface of the seeds. The plasma treatment may have broken some of the weak C-C and C-H bonds, then the C-dangle bonds may have chemically recombined with O and N elements. Thus, oxygen and nitrogen containing-functional groups such as O=C-O, C-O, C-N, C=O, and C=N bonds may have been produced on the seed surface. These polar functional groups are associated with high value-dipole moment binding energy states, thereby contributing to the greater interaction between the water droplet and the seed

surface. This leads to the decrease of contact angle and improvement of the hydrophilicity on the surfaces.^[30]

4.2. *Effect on surface morphology*

The SEM images in Figure 4.2, Figure 4.3, and Figure 4.4 show the control and treated hull of yellow corn kernels at different areas: the endosperm, the tip cap, and the germ. A comparative analysis on the surface morphology of the corn kernels revealed that the most drastic change occurred at the germ area. The control seeds had a reticulate texture while the plasma-treated seeds had an eroded surface. A similar observation was found in Figure 4.5, which presents the SEM images of the germ area of the white corn kernels at varying treatment durations. As evident in Figure 4.4 and Figure 4.5, surface erosion increased with longer plasma exposure, which typically results to better wettability and water imbibition.^[10,27]

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 4.2. SEM images of the endosperm area of the hull of yellow corn kernels which are (a) untreated (control); (b) exposed to plasma for 1s; (c) exposed to plasma for 2s; (d) exposed to plasma for 3s at a scale bar of 1mm.

ADMU MSE3494 2017/09/15 11:05 L 200 μm

(a)

ADMU MSE3507 2017/09/15 11:31 L 200 μm

(b)

ADMU MSE3503 2017/09/15 11:23 L 200 μm

(c)

ADMU MSE3498 2017/09/15 11:15 L 200 μm

(d)

Figure 4.3. SEM images of the tip cap of yellow corn kernels which are (a) untreated (control); (b) exposed to plasma for 1s; (c) exposed to plasma for 2s; (d) exposed to plasma for 3s at a scale bar of 200μm.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 4.4. SEM images of the germ area of the hull of yellow corn kernels which are (a) untreated (control); (b) exposed to plasma for 1s; (c) exposed to plasma for 2s; (d) exposed to plasma for 3s at a scale bar of 200 μ m.

Figure 4.5. SEM images of the germ area of the hull of white corn kernels which are (a) untreated (control); (b) exposed to plasma for 1s; (c) exposed to plasma for 2s; (d) exposed to plasma for 3s at a scale bar of 100μm.

4.3. Effect on wettability

The effect of plasma treatment in improving hydrophilicity was observed in the wettability test results plotted in Figure 4.6 for yellow corn kernels treated at the germ area, but it was ambiguous in those plotted in Figure 4.7 for yellow corn kernels treated at the endosperm area. In Figure 4.6, mean contact angles dropped with longer treatment durations and this trend was consistent over a minute of

observation. The 1s, 2s, and 3s-treated groups exhibited 5.63%, 9.42%, and 16.20% decrease in mean initial contact angle respectively. Moreover, plasma exposure also increased the rate water imbibition, such that the 3s-treated seeds showed the steepest downward slopes.

Figure 4.6. A time series graph showing the decrease in contact angles with longer treatment of yellow corn kernels at the germ area.

Figure 4.7. A time series graph showing the decrease in contact angles with longer treatment of yellow corn kernels at the endosperm area.

4.4. Effect on water imbibition

The time dependence of the percent weight difference shown in Figure 4.8 indicates that water imbibition increases with treatment time. The graph demonstrates the time dependence of the average water imbibition normalized by the initial masses of seeds. The 1s, 2s, and 3s-treated groups exhibited 16.26%, 31.14%, and 35.29% increase in percent weight difference respectively after four hours.

Figure 4.8. A time series graph showing the increase in water imbibition of white corn kernels with longer treatment.

4.5. Effect on germination

In both varieties of corn, Figure 4.9 and Figure 4.10 portray that the 1s-treated group consistently led with the highest germination percentage and germination rate. As seen in Figure 4.11, Figure 4.12, Figure 4.13, and Figure 4.14, plasma treatment for a duration of 1 second significantly increased the CVG and T_{mod} but shortened t_{50} and MGT.

For the yellow corn kernels treated at the endosperm area, the 2s-treated and 3s-treated groups had higher CVG and T_{mod} but lower t_{50} and MGT than the control group by protrusion, although these groups reached the same germination

percentage. On the other hand, prolonging the treatment to 3 seconds had inhibitive effects on the studied growth parameters for the white corn kernels treated at the germ area by protrusion.

Figure 4.9. A comparison of germination percentage of yellow corn kernels treated at varying durations at the endosperm area.

Figure 4.10. A comparison of germination percentage of white corn kernels treated at varying durations at the germ area.

Figure 4.11. Coefficient of velocity of germination of yellow corn kernels treated at the endosperm area and of white corn kernels treated at the germ area averaged for all trials at varying durations.

Figure 4.12. Median germination time and mean germination time of yellow corn kernels treated at varying durations at the endosperm area.

Figure 4.13. Median germination time and mean germination time averaged for all trials of white corn kernels treated at varying durations at the germ area.

Figure 4.14. Modified Timson's index of yellow corn kernels treated at the endosperm area and of white corn kernels treated at the germ area averaged for all trials at varying durations.

4.6. *Statistical Analysis*

The p-values for all germination attributes of white corn kernels were found to be less than 0.05, as shown in Appendix C. This verifies that the plasma treatment had a significant effect on germination percentage, mean germination time, median germination time, and coefficient of velocity of germination.

4.7. Correlation of surface morphology to wettability and water imbibition

The improvement in wettability and water imbibition can be attributed to changes in the chemical and physical properties of the hull due to plasma treatment. This was demonstrated by Bormashenko in lentils, beans, and wheat.^[10] As observed in the SEM images, there was evidence of surface etching provided by bombardment of charged particles and radicals formed in plasma.^[15] In the context of seed germination, etching can be considered as scarification. This could play an important role in rupturing the hull and increasing its permeability to water and gases for hard seeded species, such as corn.

The OES showed the presence of active nitrogen and oxygen species, which were generated from the gaseous compounds molecular nitrogen and triplet oxygen that predominate atmospheric air.^[11] Nitrogen oxides, such as NO or NO₂, have been used successfully to stimulate the germination of various seeds, with different authors proposing that the pretreatment process results in covalent or non-covalent attachment of plasma-produced molecular fragments on the seed envelope. In summary, the enhanced wettability may be attributed to etching^[11] and possible formation of oxygen and nitrogen-containing functional groups on the seed surface.^[6] Consequently, this promoted water imbibition and absorption of nutrients.

4.8. Correlation of surface morphology and germination

The increased wettability and water imbibition of the germ area presents plasma treatment as a physical way of breaking down dormancy.^[7] However, only the 1s-treated group exhibited the positive impact of plasma treatment on all germination attributes. For the yellow corn kernels treated at the endosperm area, faster germination occurred with longer treatment durations, but the 2s and 3s-treated

groups obtained the same germination percentage as the control group. On the other hand, all quantities were enhanced for the 1s-treated group of the white corn kernels treated at the germ area, but gradually waned for the 2s and 3s-treated groups to levels even worse than those of the control group.

It can be concluded that improvement in germination can be accomplished for shorter treatment times at the germ area, in agreement with previous studies.^[15,22]

This was probably due to the surface damage incurred by the seeds. The SEM images showed that longer plasma exposure causes more surface etching, thereby inflicting greater damage to the germ area, where the radicle and the first root emerges. The damage may have also increased the seed's susceptibility to infection.^[15] Hence, the experiments generally resulted in the 1s-treatment producing the best results.

Chapter 5

Conclusions and Recommendations

5.1. *Conclusions*

Through analyses of the SEM images and the OES of plasma, the study showed that atmospheric air plasma treatment modified the surface properties of corn kernels. The presence of N₂, O₂, NO, CO, and CN species in the OES brought about physical and chemical changes in the seed surfaces, through erosion and potential formation of polar functional groups, and led to improved wettability and water imbibition of the corn kernels treated at the germ area. As the treatment was prolonged, mean contact angles dropped and water imbibition escalated.

Based on the daily germination count, only the 1s treatment period in the germ area improved all germination attributes as compared to the control group. The germination percentage increased by 19.05% and 4.65% respectively for yellow corn kernels treated in the endosperm area and for white corn kernels treated in the germ area. Furthermore, the 1s-treated group of the white corn kernels showed an increase of 9.41% for the CVG and 5.16% for the T_{mod}, then the following decreases: 7.56% for the t₅₀ by Coolbear et al., 7.35% for the t₅₀ by Farooq et al., and 8.65% for MGT. For the yellow corn kernels, the longer plasma treatment resulted to higher CVG, higher T_{mod}, lower t₅₀, and lower MGT, but the control, 2s-treated, 3s-treated groups reached the same germination percentage. On the other hand, the prolonged exposure of seeds to plasma caused excessive erosion of the germ area of white corn kernels, leading to adverse effects on germination.

5.2. Recommendations

The results support the supposition of the former researchers, but more evidence is needed to prove the underlying mechanism of the plasma interaction with living tissues and cells.

Appendices

Appendix A.

(a)

(b)

Figure A.1. Actual photos of the atmospheric air plasma jet system (a) zoomed in and (b) connected with the Arduino microcontroller setup.

(a)

(b)

Figure A.2. (a) A diagram and (b) an actual photo of the Arduino microcontroller setup.

```
int LEDPin=12;

int waitTimeOn=620;

int waitTimeOff=1000;

void setup() {

    pinMode(LEDPin,OUTPUT);// Sets
the mode of the LEDpin 12

}

void loop() {

    digitalWrite(LEDPin,HIGH); //
Switches ON the transistor

    delay(waitTimeOn);// Time for the
transistor to be ON state

    digitalWrite(LEDPin,LOW);//
Switches OFF the transistor

    delay(waitTimeOff);// Time for the
transistor to be on the OFF state

}
```

(a)

```
int LEDPin=12;

int waitTimeOn=620;

int waitTimeOff=2000;

void setup() {

    pinMode(LEDPin,OUTPUT);// Sets
the mode of the LEDpin 12

}

void loop() {

    digitalWrite(LEDPin,HIGH); //
Switches ON the transistor

    delay(waitTimeOn);// Time for the
transistor to be ON state

    digitalWrite(LEDPin,LOW);//
Switches OFF the transistor

    delay(waitTimeOff);// Time for the
transistor to be on the OFF state

}
```

(b)

int LEDPin=12;	void loop() {
int waitTimeOn=620; // in	digitalWrite(LEDPin,HIGH); //
milliseconds	Switches ON the transistor
int waitTimeOff=3000; // in	delay(waitTimeOn);// Duration that
milliseconds	the transistor is in ON state
void setup() {	digitalWrite(LEDPin,LOW);//
pinMode(LEDPin,OUTPUT);// Sets	Switches OFF the transistor
the mode of the LEDpin 12	delay(waitTimeOff);// Duration that
}	the transistor is in OFF state
	}

(c)

Figure. A.3. Arduino codes used for the (a) 1s, (b) 2s, and (c) 3s treatment durations.

Figure. A.4. An actual photo of the contact angle measurement set up.

Figure. A.5. An actual photo of the germination set up.

Appendix B.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure. B.1. (a) Control, (b) 1s, (c) 2s, and (d) 3s treatment groups of white corn seeds on third day of germination.

Appendix C.

Table C.1. ANOVA results for the germination attributes of white corn kernels based on germination count upon protrusion of the radicle: (a) germination percentage, (b) median germination time (t50) according to Coolbear et al., (c) median germination time (t50) according to Farooq et al., (d) mean germination time, and (e) coefficient of velocity of germination.

ANOVA: Single Factor

GermPercent

DESCRIPTION					Alpha	0.01			
<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Variance</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>Std Err</i>	<i>Lower</i>	<i>Upper</i>	
1s	3	266.66667	88.888889	103.7037	207.40741	5.7972133	69.436993	108.34078	
2s	3	204.44444	68.148148	179.42387	358.84774	5.7972133	48.696252	87.600044	
3s	3	120	40	19.753086	39.506173	5.7972133	20.548104	59.451896	
control	3	242.22222	80.740741	100.41152	200.82305	5.7972133	61.288845	100.19264	

ANOVA

<i>Sources</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P value</i>	<i>F crit</i>	<i>RMSSE</i>	<i>Omega Sq</i>
Between Groups	4123.0453	3	1374.3484	13.631293	0.0016441	7.5909919	2.1316107	0.7594895
Within Groups	806.58436	8	100.82305					
Total	4929.6296	11	448.14815					

(a)

ANOVA: Single Factor

t50_Coolbear

DESCRIPTION					Alpha	0.01			
<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Variance</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>Std Err</i>	<i>Lower</i>	<i>Upper</i>	
1s	3	6.236105	2.0787017	0.000522	0.001044	0.0480396	1.9175101	2.2398932	
2s	3	6.9267544	2.3089181	0.0028117	0.0056234	0.0480396	2.1477265	2.4701097	
3s	3	7.1134992	2.3711664	0.0143493	0.0286987	0.0480396	2.2099748	2.532358	
control	3	6.9915053	2.3305018	0.0100107	0.0200213	0.0480396	2.1693102	2.4916934	

ANOVA

<i>Sources</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P value</i>	<i>F crit</i>	<i>RMSSE</i>	<i>Omega Sq</i>
Between Groups	0.1559497	3	0.0519832	7.5083144	0.0103179	7.5909919	1.582015	0.619349
Within Groups	0.0553874	8	0.0069234					
Total	0.211337	11	0.0192125					

(b)

ANOVA: Single Factor

t50_Farooq

DESCRIPTION					Alpha	0.01			
<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Variance</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>Std Err</i>	<i>Lower</i>	<i>Upper</i>	
1s	3	6.1565679	2.0521893	0.0005418	0.0010836	0.0436399	1.9057606	2.198618	
2s	3	6.7991228	2.2663743	0.0019008	0.0038017	0.0436399	2.1199456	2.412803	

3s	3	6.8944193	2.2981398	0.01176	0.02352	0.0436399	2.1517111	2.4445685
control	3	6.882901	2.2943003	0.0086506	0.0173012	0.0436399	2.1478716	2.440729

ANOVA

Sources	SS	df	MS	F	P value	F crit	RMSSE	Omega Sq
Between Groups	0.1250912	3	0.0416971	7.2982237	0.0111843	7.5909919	1.5597247	0.6115835
Within Groups	0.0457065	8	0.0057133					
Total	0.1707977	11	0.0155271					

(c)

ANOVA: Single Factor MeanGermTime

DESCRIPTION		Alpha 0.01						
Groups	Count	Sum	Mean	Variance	SS	Std Err	Lower	Upper
1s	3	9.1478632	3.0492877	0.0004502	0.0009005	0.0356888	2.929538	3.1690375
2s	3	9.6691892	3.2230631	0.0024606	0.0049212	0.0356888	3.1033133	3.3428128
3s	3	9.7333333	3.2444444	0.0084259	0.0168519	0.0356888	3.1246947	3.3641942
control	3	9.7297595	3.2432532	0.0039475	0.0078951	0.0356888	3.1235034	3.3630029

ANOVA

Sources	SS	df	MS	F	P value	F crit	RMSSE	Omega Sq
Between Groups	0.0800796	3	0.0266932	6.9857917	0.0126477	7.5909919	1.5259742	0.5994309
Within Groups	0.0305686	8	0.0038211					
Total	0.1106482	11	0.0100589					

(d)

ANOVA: Single Factor CVG

DESCRIPTION		Alpha 0.01						
Groups	Count	Sum	Mean	Variance	SS	Std Err	Lower	Upper
1s	3	98.386816	32.795605	0.0523766	0.1047531	0.3424764	31.646464	33.944746
2s	3	93.093737	31.031246	0.2243013	0.4486027	0.3424764	29.882105	32.180387
3s	3	92.515263	30.838421	0.7657472	1.5314943	0.3424764	29.68928	31.987562
control	3	92.523127	30.841042	0.3650559	0.7301117	0.3424764	29.691901	31.990183

ANOVA

Sources	SS	df	MS	F	P value	F crit	RMSSE	Omega Sq
Between Groups	8.1279136	3	2.7093045	7.6997264	0.0096003	7.5909919	1.6020535	0.6261587
Within Groups	2.8149619	8	0.3518702					
Total	10.942876	11	0.9948069					

(e)

Table C.2. ANOVA results for the germination attributes of white corn kernels based on germination count once the radicle has reached half the length of the seed: (a) germination percentage, (b) median germination time (t50) according to Coolbear et al., (c) median germination time (t50) according to Farooq et al., (d) mean germination time, and (e) coefficient of velocity of germination.

ANOVA: Single Factor GermPercent

DESCRIPTION					Alpha	0.01			
<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Variance</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>Std Err</i>	<i>Lower</i>	<i>Upper</i>	
1s	3.0000	266.6667	88.8889	103.7037	207.4074	5.7972	69.4370	108.3408	
2s	3.0000	204.4444	68.1481	179.4239	358.8477	5.7972	48.6963	87.6000	
3s	3.0000	120.0000	40.0000	19.7531	39.5062	5.7972	20.5481	59.4519	
control	3.0000	242.2222	80.7407	100.4115	200.8230	5.7972	61.2888	100.1926	

ANOVA

<i>Sources</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P value</i>	<i>F crit</i>	<i>RMSSE</i>	<i>Omega Sq</i>
Between Groups	4123.0453	3.0000	1374.3484	13.6313	0.0016	7.5910	2.1316	0.7595
Within Groups	806.5844	8.0000	100.8230					
Total	4929.6296	11.0000	448.1481					

(a)

ANOVA: Single Factor t50_Coolbear

DESCRIPTION					Alpha	0.0100			
<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Variance</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>Std Err</i>	<i>Lower</i>	<i>Upper</i>	
1s	3.0000	7.1875	2.3958	0.0042	0.0083	0.0232	2.3180	2.4737	
2s	3.0000	9.3500	3.1167	0.0002	0.0004	0.0232	3.0388	3.1945	
3s	3.0000	10.6409	3.5470	0.0021	0.0041	0.0232	3.4691	3.6248	
control	3.0000	10.2631	3.4210	0.0000	0.0000	0.0232	3.3432	3.4989	

ANOVA

<i>Sources</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P value</i>	<i>F crit</i>	<i>RMSSE</i>	<i>Omega Sq</i>
Between Groups	2.3920	3.0000	0.7973	493.9836	0.0000	7.5910	12.8320	0.9920
Within Groups	0.0129	8.0000	0.0016					
Total	2.4050	11.0000	0.2186					

(b)

ANOVA: Single Factor t50_Farooq

DESCRIPTION					Alpha	0.0100			
<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Variance</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>Std Err</i>	<i>Lower</i>	<i>Upper</i>	
1s	3.0000	7.0848	2.3616	0.0044	0.0087	0.0237	2.2822	2.4410	
2s	3.0000	9.2229	3.0743	0.0003	0.0006	0.0237	2.9949	3.1537	
3s	3.0000	10.5000	3.5000	0.0021	0.0041	0.0237	3.4206	3.5794	
control	3.0000	10.2038	3.4013	0.0000	0.0000	0.0237	3.3219	3.4807	

ANOVA

<i>Sources</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P value</i>	<i>F crit</i>	<i>RMSSE</i>	<i>Omega Sq</i>
Between Groups	2.3870	3.0000	0.7957	473.3597	0.0000	7.5910	12.5613	0.9916
Within Groups	0.0134	8.0000	0.0017					
Total	2.4005	11.0000	0.2182					

(c)

ANOVA: Single Factor

MeanGermTime

DESCRIPTION					Alpha		0.0100	
<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Variance</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>Std Err</i>	<i>Lower</i>	<i>Upper</i>
1s	3.0000	9.9688	3.3229	0.0008	0.0016	0.0357	3.2031	3.4428
2s	3.0000	11.0023	3.6674	0.0094	0.0188	0.0357	3.5476	3.7873
3s	3.0000	12.0569	4.0190	0.0042	0.0084	0.0357	3.8991	4.1388
control	3.0000	11.6073	3.8691	0.0009	0.0018	0.0357	3.7493	3.9889

ANOVA

<i>Sources</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P value</i>	<i>F crit</i>	<i>RMSSE</i>	<i>Omega Sq</i>
Between Groups	0.8161	3.0000	0.2720	71.0790	0.0000	7.5910	4.8675	0.9460
Within Groups	0.0306	8.0000	0.0038					
Total	0.8467	11.0000	0.0770					

(d)

ANOVA: Single Factor

CVG

DESCRIPTION					Alpha		0.0100	
<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Variance</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>Std Err</i>	<i>Lower</i>	<i>Upper</i>
1s	3.0000	90.2860	30.0953	0.0649	0.1298	0.2571	29.2327	30.9579
2s	3.0000	81.8390	27.2797	0.5237	1.0473	0.2571	26.4171	28.1423
3s	3.0000	74.6589	24.8863	0.1642	0.3284	0.2571	24.0237	25.7489
control	3.0000	77.5405	25.8468	0.0403	0.0807	0.2571	24.9842	26.7095

ANOVA

<i>Sources</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P value</i>	<i>F crit</i>	<i>RMSSE</i>	<i>Omega Sq</i>
Between Groups	46.3617	3.0000	15.4539	77.9407	0.0000	7.5910	5.0971	0.9506
Within Groups	1.5862	8.0000	0.1983					
Total	47.9479	11.0000	4.3589					

(e)

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